

“RESEARCH-BASED TRANSFORMATION OF TEACHER EDUCATION: TRADITION AS A BASIS FOR INNOVATION” International Conference on Teacher Education

SOCIOLINGUISTIC APPROACH IN LANGUAGE LEARNING PROCESS

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Abstract. *Language as a social phenomenon requires us to learn it from sociolinguistic point of view for effectively communicating with interlocutors in different situations without any misunderstandings. The best way of enhancing reading comprehension and communication skills in non-linguistic universities is sociolinguistic approach which will be defined based on different scientists' views in our article.*

Globalisation process in all sphere of life demands educators to learn and implement modern tendencies of education especially in second language acquisition process. Many researchers asserted that learning grammar, morphology, syntaxis and vocabulary are not enough. Professor Arlene Clachar has 20 years teaching experience who devoted her life for learning culture's link with language usage noticed essence of sociolinguistic aspect in language learning. As a selected member by U.S. Department of States worked in project to learn residents of different societies and their speech behavior and culture's affect to language and by collecting data which can be used in these countries education system for teaching speech acts. Elaine Tarone defined that this sociolinguistic approach help learners to distinguish sociolinguistic factors which have impact on cognitive process of language acquisition and linguistic system. [1,p. 837] Dr Pedro Tavarez and Francheska Reyes gave the same definition as Elaine Tarone connected to cognitive function of learning new linguistic rules based on social factors. Kuznetsova Marina Nikolayevna in her works confirmed that role plays are crucial in developing sociolinguistic approach of non-philological university students. Author divided speech of non-philological direction students into 3 types:

- 1 social and household
- 2 academic
- 3 professional

Kuznetsova Marina Nikolayevna considered that English as an international language should be taught with all sociolinguistic features. She asserted that international communication of non-philological university students' in academic and professional speech requires them to know verbal, nonverbal elements of language. Belenyuk Natalya Aleksandrovna claimed that international communication in foreign language requires learners to learn language based on sociolinguistic

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approach. This approach includes all key sociolinguistic peculiarities of foreign language and help learners to avoid speech mistakes when they converse with foreigners. Dyakova Mariana Yurevna confirms that degree of formality of speech not only linked with social features but also social distance, social status, gender, and age. She emphasized on distance of interlocutor as a main aspect and divides it into two types social and private U o'zining ishida urg'uni muloqotchilarning orasidagi masofaga qaratadi (ijtimoiy va xususiy masofa) hissiy-intanatsion tasvir yoshga doir rasmiylik bilan tanlnadigan(Koltunova 2000). Rasmiy muloqotning oldindan yuklatilgan komponentlari : muloqotchilarning ijtimoiy roli, maqsad, vositalar va muloqot joyi.(13 b)

T.N Astafurova classified formal speech into 3 types:

1. Ascending type- consists of conditional and interrogative sentences of employee and boss which are full of fear and respect tone qo'rqqoq va hurmat tonda

2 Descending type- boss's attitude towards the employee by using strict affirmative command sentences.

3 Horizontal type-includes itself equal colleagues friendship which leads to cooperation._(Astifurova 1994 15). Sociolinguistic aspect of communication defines not only topic but also action program of speech. Sociolinguistic aspect includes different components for communication:

- The speaker and his social role,
- The listener and his social role,
- Relationship among interlocutors,
- Intonation of communication,
- Aids,
- Road,
- The place of communication(Krisin 1989)

Suxareva Tatyana Nikolayevna stated that representatives of these approach avoided using unimportant phrases (units) in their speech which lead us: distraction, to forget, decreasing interest, pronunciation mistakes and grammatical forms. They consider that knowing language perfect is not required but acquiring necessary enough knowledge and skills are important which help us to understand independently and try to correct mistakes of our interlocutor are enough. Based on all above analyzed works we can make conclusion that sociolinguistic approach is best way of enhancing their speech but also their reading skills because students always interested in learning about culture and its influence on language when they communicate with native speakers in different social situations. In non-linguistic

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universities sociolinguistic aspect of language is not covered enough in their syllabus even they have different cultural topics such as: lifestyle, holidays, travel tourism so we decided to create suitable manual for enhancing their reading comprehension based on sociolinguistic approach.

Reference:

1. Elaine T. Sociolinguistic approaches to second language acquisition research - 1997-2007 p 832
2. Дьякова М. финских учащихся речевой реализации стратегии компромисса в сфере делового общения :диссертация... кандидат пед наук :130002 Санкт Петербург, 2006 -244 с.
3. Кузнецова М. Лингводидактические основы использования ролевой игры как средство формирования навыков межкультурного общения на иностранном языке на материале преподавания английского языка неязыковым вузе: стр28
4. Кузнецова М. Лингводидактические основы использования ролевой игры как средство формирования навыков межкультурного общения на иностранном языке на материале преподавания английского языка неязыковым вузе: стр 87
5. Dr Pedro Tavaréz and Francheska Reyes Sociolinguistic approaches in EFL teaching methods for Dominican college students: p-20
6. Сухарева Т. Формирование коммуникативных стратегий словоупотребления у студентов неязыково вуза: стр 11